

HEAD TEACHERS' PERCEPTION OF THE ROLE OF SCHOOL MANAGEMENT TEAM IN ENSURING ACCESS TO EDUCATION AND INFRASTRUCTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract: *The main purpose of the study was to ascertain head teacher's perception of the role of school management team in ensuring access to education and infrastructural development in primary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study. The study adopted the descriptive research design. The population of the study comprised 1070 head teachers in government owned primary schools in Anambra State. The sample of the study comprised 291 head teachers in public primary schools in Anambra State. Questionnaire was used to collect data for the study. The instrument was validated by three experts in education. The reliability of the instrument was determined through a pilot test. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. The finding of the study revealed that head teachers opined that school management team ensures access to education in primary school in Anambra State to a low extent. Conversely, findings revealed that head teachers opined that school management team ensures infrastructural development in primary school in Anambra State to a high extent. Based on these findings, the researcher recommended among others that School management teams in primary schools should actively engage with parents, communities, and local leaders to raise awareness about the free and compulsory education policy.*

Keywords: *School Management Team (SMT), Role, Access, Infrastructural Development, Primary Schools*

Introduction

Primary education in Nigeria constitutes the foundational stage of formal learning, primarily catering to children aged between six and twelve. Primary education is of critical importance as it provides the basic building blocks for future educational endeavours. Primary education refers to the formal

education provided in institutions for children aged 6 to 11 years and above (Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN), 2014). It represents the initial and mandatory phase of education. The curriculum at this level is structured to ensure that pupils acquire fundamental literacy and numeracy skills, which are essential for effective communication, problem-solving, and academic progression (Aduwa & Omajuwa, 2021). According to the FRN (2014), primary education aims to instil values such as discipline, social responsibility, and a lifelong interest in learning. This level is preceded by nursery or pre-school education and followed by secondary education. Primary education encompasses the first six years of the nine-year basic education framework, which aligns with the Universal Basic Education (UBE) standard. Often referred to as elementary education, this stage is a foundational component of the educational system.

The UBE programme encompasses six years of primary education and three years of junior secondary education. It also includes adult and non-formal education initiatives to accommodate individuals who left school prematurely (Aja et al., 2024). Aja et al. explained that the UBE program is designed to provide free access to education, significantly reduce school dropout rates, align education with learners' needs, and promote lifelong learning. The main aim of UBE is meeting the essential educational needs of children, adolescents, youth, and adults. Similarly, Uyang et al. (2017) opined that the UBE programme prioritizes holistic education rather than mere schooling. It seeks to develop the child comprehensively, fostering a lifelong learning process that enhances literacy levels among both children and adults. Uyang et al. (2017) pointed out that the overarching goal of the UBE programme is to establish a foundation for lifelong learning by instilling appropriate knowledge, self-awareness, citizenship, and life skills. The UBEC (2010) Act provides a comprehensive framework for implementing and maintaining minimum standards for Universal Basic Education in Nigeria. These standards ensure that basic education is accessible, quality education standards, infrastructure development, monitoring and evaluating and adequate funding, ultimately contributing to national development.

The Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC) Act is built on the foundation of providing free, compulsory, and universal basic education for all children of school-going age in Nigeria. This initiative seeks to ensure that every child, regardless of their background, has the opportunity to access education. One of the primary objectives of the Act is to eliminate barriers to education such as financial constraints, cultural practices, and geographical location (Aja et al., 2024). This ensures that no child is excluded from receiving an education due to these challenges (Obanya, 2017). Furthermore, the Act calls for the expansion of education access by establishing more schools in underserved or rural areas, where children might otherwise have limited access to educational institutions. Special attention is also given to vulnerable groups, including children with disabilities, ensuring that the education system is inclusive and accessible to all children, promoting equality of opportunity (Aja et al., 2024). To achieve this, it is essential that physical infrastructure is adequately provided.

The UBEC Act also places great importance on infrastructure development to support the delivery of quality education. It mandates the provision of adequate school facilities, including well-equipped classrooms, libraries, and laboratories, to ensure that pupils have access to the necessary resources for effective learning (Emeka & Olaole, 2015). These facilities must be designed to be child-friendly, with safe, supportive, and conducive learning environments (Ojo & Azeez, 2024). The implementation of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme in Anambra State has encountered significant challenges, hindering its effectiveness in achieving its objectives. A major issue is the state's inability to access over N2.6 billion in matching grants from the Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC) due to the lack of counterpart funding (Lawal & Agbajileke, 2024). This financial shortfall has resulted in insufficient resources for critical areas such as infrastructure, teacher training, and the provision of educational materials. The inadequate infrastructure in many primary schools further compounds the problem. Numerous schools operate in poor conditions, including overcrowded classrooms, lack of proper furniture, and inadequate sanitation, which hinder effective learning and reduce enrolment and retention rates (Asiegbu et al., 2023). These issues have also contributed to a high rate of out-of-school children in the state, as poor facilities and limited access to quality education prevent many children from attending school (Asiegbu et al., 2023). Although the UBE programme aims to provide free and compulsory education, its ineffective implementation in Anambra State has left a significant number of children without schooling. Moreover, poor educational outcomes are prevalent, with many teachers inadequately trained and lacking the resources necessary for effective instruction (Lawal & Agbajileke, 2024). Addressing these challenges is crucial to ensuring the success of the UBE programme in the state. This has increased the call for the involvement of school management team for the facilitation of the implementation of UBE in primary schools.

The school management team refers to the organisational structure responsible for overseeing the day-to-day operations of the school and implementing its policies. The school management team refers to the top officers in the school such as the Head teachers, deputy head teacher, the heads of departments and form teachers have the responsibility to plan, organize, lead and implement school policies; as well as evaluate staff performance in the teaching-learning process within the school (Nwangwa & Omotere, 2018). Additionally, school management team plays a pivotal role in determining the most effective way to align the school's categorisation with the broader vision of its community (Klinck et al., 2023). A key responsibility of the SMT is resource management, which includes addressing issues such as inadequate infrastructure and insufficient teaching materials. Furthermore, the SMT proactively engages with stakeholders, including parents and community members, to foster collective responsibility for education and raise awareness about the programme's objectives. In terms of infrastructural development, the SMT monitors and evaluates school facilities, identifying areas needing improvement and implementing interventions to ensure compliance with UBE standards. This includes addressing overcrowded classrooms, lack of proper furniture, and inadequate sanitation facilities, which are

critical for enhancing access to quality education (Asiegbu et al., 2023). However, these views have not been empirically proven to be true in primary schools in Anambra State. It is against this background that the researcher investigated head teachers' perception of the role of school management team in ensuring access to education and infrastructural development in primary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Primary education is a critical stage of education in Nigeria, serving as the foundation for subsequent learning and development. Under the Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme, children at the primary education level are entitled to free and compulsory education. This mandate was further emphasised by the Anambra State Governor, who declared free and mandatory education for all children within the basic education framework. However, despite this policy declaration, it appears that some children in the state are still not attending school. Interactions with some parents suggest a lack of awareness of the government's policy on free education. Others report concerns about the payment of fees, as pupils in Mission Public Schools are still required to pay certain charges. Additionally, the researcher observes that some public schools reveal inadequate infrastructure, with a lack of basic health amenities and essential educational resources needed for effective learning. The researcher is concerned that if these issues persist, they may significantly hinder the achievement of the UBE programme's objectives in Anambra State. The therefore wonders if the school management team plays any role in improving access to education and infrastructural development in primary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain head teachers' perception of the role of school management team in ensuring access to education and infrastructural development in primary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study determined head teachers' perception of the:

1. extent of school management team involvement in ensuring access to education in primary schools in Anambra State
2. extent of school management team involvement in ensuring infrastructural development in primary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent is school management team involved in ensuring access to education in primary schools in Anambra State?
2. To what extent is school management team involved in ensuring infrastructural development in primary schools in Anambra State?

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey design. This design was considered suitable because it allowed the researcher to collect data directly from headteachers of public primary schools in Anambra State.

The study was carried out in Anambra State, located in the South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The population of the study included all 1,070 headteachers in government-owned primary schools in Anambra State. Their distribution across the six education zones was as follows: Aguata Zone – 172, Awka Zone – 194, Nnewi Zone – 249, Ogidi Zone – 168, Onitsha Zone – 127, and Otuocha Zone – 160. This information was obtained from the Universal Basic Education Board, Personnel Department, Awka Headquarters, in July 2021. Taro Yamane’s formula was used to determine the sample size, as it was an appropriate sampling method for the study. This formula is often applied in research to calculate a representative sample size from a known population while maintaining a specified level of precision. In this study, the total population of interest consists of 1,070 head teachers from government-owned primary schools in Anambra State. Using a precision level of 0.05 (5% margin of error), the formula is applied as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Substituting the values $N=1070$ and $e=0.05$, the calculation proceeds as:

$$n = \frac{1070}{1 + 1070(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1070}{1 + 2.675}$$

$$n = \frac{1070}{3.675}$$

$$n = 291$$

Thus, the sample size for the study is determined to be approximately 291 head teachers. This ensures that the sample is large enough to provide reliable and generalizable findings while still being manageable for the study. To achieve fairness and representativeness, the calculated sample size was distributed proportionally across the six education zones in Anambra State based on their respective population sizes. The formula used for proportional allocation is:

$$n_i = \frac{N_i}{N} \times n$$

Where n_i is the sample size for each zone, N_i is the population of each zone, N is the total population, and n is the total sample size (291).

1. Aguata Zone: $n_i = \frac{172}{N1070} \times 291 = 47$
2. Awka Zone: $n_i = \frac{194}{N1070} \times 291 = 53$
3. Nnewi Zone: $n_i = \frac{249}{N1070} \times 291 = 68$
4. Ogidi Zone: $n_i = \frac{168}{N1070} \times 291 = 46$
5. Onitsha Zone: $n_i = \frac{127}{N1070} \times 291 = 35$
6. Otuocha Zone: $n_i = \frac{160}{N1070} \times 291 = 44$

This adds up to approximately 291, reflecting the determined sample size. This proportional approach ensures that each zone is fairly represented in the study, aligning with the relative sizes of their populations.

The instruments that was used for data collection was a questionnaire titled “Role of School Management Team in Ensuring Access to Education and Infrastructural Development in Primary School Questionnaire (RSMTAEIDPSQ), The questionnaire contains 20 items arranged in two clusters, A and B. Cluster A has 10 items on the extent school management team is involved in ensuring access to education in primary schools and Cluster B has 10 items on the extent school management team is involved in ensuring infrastructural development in primary schools. The instrument is structured on a four-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). The instrument was validated by two lecturers in the Department of Educational Management and Policy and one lecturer in Measurement and Evaluation, Unit in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University University, Igbariam Campus. The instrument was administered to 20 head teachers in Enugu State for trial testing. The data collected were analyzed using Cronbach alpha to find out the internal consistency reliability of the instrument. Cronbach alpha was used because it is considered best for aggregate scores of instruments with multiple items. The result of the analysis yielded reliability coefficient index 0.83 for cluster A and 0.80 for cluster B. The overall of reliability coefficient index of 0.82 was obtained and this showed that the instrument was reliable for the study. Instrument was directly administered to the respondents by the researcher with the help of three research assistants. Out of 291 copies of the instrument administered, 268 copies were returned in good condition and used for the analysis of data for the study. Data collected in the study were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and determine the closeness of respondents’ responses respectively. The decision rule for this study was based on the interpretation of mean ratings. Any item with a mean rating of 2.50 and above was considered to indicate a high extent, reflecting significant contributions or roles. Conversely, any item with a mean rating below 2.50 was interpreted as a low extent, indicating minimal or limited contributions or roles.

Results

Research Question One

To what extent is school management team involved in ensuring access to education in primary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean ratings of Head Teachers on the Extent School Management Team Involvement in Ensuring Access to Education in Primary Schools in Anambra State (N=268)

S/N	Item Statements	Mea n	SD	Remarks
1.	Identifies and supports pupils who are at risk of dropping out.	2.22	0.76	Low Extent
2.	Conducts awareness programs on the benefits of education for all.	2.11	0.73	Low Extent
3.	Organizes campaigns to enroll out-of-school children.	2.34	0.84	Low Extent
4.	Monitors attendance records to ensure regular pupil participation.	2.70	0.89	High Extent
5.	Provides financial assistance or scholarships to pupils in need.	2.35	0.81	Low Extent
6.	Supplies textbooks and writing materials to pupils.	2.00	0.78	Low Extent
7.	Creates policies to include children with disabilities in learning.	2.16	0.75	Low Extent
8.	Conducts parent-teacher meetings to address barriers to education.	2.56	0.70	High Extent
9.	Partners with local organizations to support school programs.	3.00	0.83	High Extent
10.	Implements security measures to ensure pupil safety.	3.10	0.81	High Extent
	Cluster Mean	2.45		Low Extent

Data in Table 1 revealed that school management team carry out items 4, 8, 9 and 10 with mean ratings ranging between 2.70 and 3.10 to a high extent. However, they rated items 1, 2, 3, 5, 6 and 7 with mean ratings ranging between 2.00 and 2.35 to a low extent. The standard deviation score ranging between 0.70 and 0.89 indicate that the respondents' opinions were related. The cluster mean of 2.45 indicate that head teachers opined that school management team ensures access to education in primary school in Anambra State to a low extent.

Research Question Two

To what extent is school management team involved in ensuring infrastructural development in primary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Mean ratings of Head Teachers on the Extent School Management Team Involvement in Ensuring Infrastructural Development in Primary Schools in Anambra State (N=268)

S/N	Item Statements	Mea	SD	Remarks
		n		
11.	Constructs new classrooms to increase pupil capacity.	2.04	0.70	Low Extent
12.	Renovates damaged classrooms for improved learning conditions.	2.50	0.75	High Extent
13	Provides desks for pupils.	2.65	0.80	High Extent
14	Provides chairs for teachers.	2.56	0.73	High Extent
15.	Installs water facilities for hygiene purposes.	2.30	0.85	Low Extent
16.	Builds toilet facilities for pupils.	2.45	0.81	Low Extent
17.	Installs fences to secure school premises.	2.50	0.77	High Extent
18.	Provides electricity to power learning activities.	2.21	0.70	Low Extent
19.	Constructs playgrounds for physical activities.	2.86	0.74	High Extent
20.	Supplies chalkboards for classrooms.	3.22	0.88	High Extent
	Cluster Mean	2.52		Low Extent

Data in Table 1 revealed that school management team carry out items 12, 13, 14, 17, 19 and 20 with mean ratings ranging between 2.50 and 3.22 to a high extent. However, they rated items 11, 15, 16 and 18 with mean ratings ranging between 2.04 and 2.45 to a low extent. The standard deviation score ranging between 0.70 and 0.88 indicate that the respondents' opinions were close. The cluster mean of 2.45 indicate that head teachers opined that school management team ensures infrastructural development in primary school in Anambra State to a high extent.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study revealed that head teachers opined that school management team ensures access to education in primary school in Anambra State to a low extent. The finding of the study may have resulted because, inadequate funding may limit the ability of school management teams to implement initiatives that improve access to education. Many public schools in Nigeria, particularly in Anambra State, operate under constrained budgets, which hinders their capacity to provide essential resources, conduct enrollment campaigns, or address the specific needs of marginalized children. The lack of sufficient financial support from the government or external stakeholders directly affects the ability of school management teams to fulfill their roles effectively. Also, insufficient training and capacity-building for members of the school management team could account for this finding. When members lack the necessary skills or understanding of how to enhance access to education, their efforts may remain uncoordinated and ineffective. This is particularly true in addressing complex challenges

such as inclusivity, dropout prevention, and community engagement, which require strategic planning and collaborative efforts. These findings are in agreement is in line with Asiegbu et al. (2023) who stated that highlighted the critical role of funding in improving educational access, noting that many Nigerian schools struggle to provide basic infrastructure due to limited financial resources. Similarly, Aja et al. (2024) emphasized the importance of professional development for school management teams, arguing that the lack of training significantly hampers their ability to create inclusive and equitable educational environments.

Furthermore, the finding of the study revealed that head teachers opined that school management team ensures infrastructural development in primary school in Anambra State to a high extent. This finding implies that the management team actively prioritizes creating a conducive learning environment through the provision of adequate infrastructure. One possible explanation for this finding is the influence of government policies and funding mechanisms aimed at improving primary education. Programs such as the Universal Basic Education (UBE) initiative have emphasized the importance of addressing infrastructural gaps in schools, providing financial and material support to enhance the quality of education. These policies may have encouraged school management teams to focus on infrastructure as a key component of their responsibilities. Another possible explanation is the active involvement of local communities in the education process. In many parts of Anambra State, community stakeholders, including Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs) and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), play a significant role in supporting schools. This collaborative effort may have motivated school management teams to maximize available resources and foster infrastructural development. Contributions from these stakeholders often complement government funding, enabling schools to achieve significant improvements in physical facilities. This finding is in agreement with Ojo and Azeez (2024), who reported that effective leadership by school management teams was critical to improving school infrastructure in Nigerian primary schools. Ojo and Azeez highlighted the importance of strategic planning and the ability of management teams to mobilize resources for development. Similarly, Nwangwa and Omotere (2018) found that schools with proactive management teams benefited from better infrastructure due to their ability to effectively utilize government grants and engage with community stakeholders. However, the findings contrast with the observations of Asiegbu et al. (2023), who noted that infrastructural development in primary schools was moderate in many parts of Nigeria due to inconsistent funding and limited collaboration among stakeholders. This difference could be due to regional differences in policy implementation and resource distribution. In Anambra State, the presence of strong community-school partnerships and consistent government support may explain the higher extent of infrastructural development reported in this study.

Conclusion

The researcher concludes, based on the findings of the study, that school management teams play a significant role in ensuring infrastructural development in primary schools in Anambra State. However,

their role in ensuring access to education in primary schools is minimal. Therefore, it is imperative that targeted efforts and measures are implemented to strengthen the role of the school management teams in promoting access to education, ensuring that all children have the opportunity to attend school and benefit from the provisions of the Universal Basic Education programme.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher proffered the following recommendations:

1. School management teams in primary schools should actively engage with parents, communities, and local leaders to raise awareness about the free and compulsory education policy. They should collaborate with relevant stakeholders to ensure that all eligible children are enrolled and attending school. Furthermore, the Anambra State Government should provide additional support to SMTs by offering regular training and resources to effectively communicate the benefits of the Universal Basic Education programme to parents and communities.

2. While the SMTs have played a significant role in infrastructural development in primary schools in Anambra State, they should focus more on critical areas such as building new classrooms, constructing toilet facilities, providing electricity, and installing pipe-borne water. SMTs should prioritise these essential needs and seek community involvement in the planning and execution of these projects. Furthermore, the Local Government Authorities should collaborate with the State Government to allocate more resources for infrastructure development in primary schools, particularly in rural areas.

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